

NOTES

Electrical Conductivity of Negatively charged Iron Oxide Sol

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Negatively charged iron oxide sol is prepared by peptizing ferric hydroxide with ammonium hydroxide in presence of sucrose. The micelles behave as a colloidal electrolyte in the sense that on dilution equivalent conductivity of micelles first decreases and then increases on further dilution. Ageing results in increase of conductivity of the sol. Purification of the sol decreases the conductivity.

The negatively charged iron oxide sol may be prepared by peptizing freshly precipitated ferric hydroxide with minimum quantity of ammonium hydroxide in the presence of Sucrose^{1,2}. The electrical conductivity of positively charged iron oxide sol was previously determined³.

EXPERIMENTAL

The preparation of the sol has been reported before⁴. The sol contains hydroxyl as a stabilizing ion and ammonium as a gegenion. The presence of sucrose is essential for the stability of the sol. The sols E, F, G, H were employed for conductivity determination. The concentration of sol H is given below. The other sols were similar in type.

Sol H: Fe_2O_3 —11.76 g./l., Sucrose—6.213%, Chloride—2.232 m. eq./l., Ammonia in traces, $\text{pH}=7.1$.

Change in conductivity on ageing: The conductivity of negatively charged iron oxide sol is measured over a number of days. It is observed that dilution with water results in rendering the sol unstable. Hence the sol was diluted with sucrose solution of suitable concentration as near as possible to the concentration of sucrose in the original sol. Increase of conductivity due to addition of sucrose was neglected. The conductivity of the sols was measured at $36.0^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ (loc. cit.)

Change in conductivity on dilution: Sols G and H after dilution with 40% sucrose solution were employed for conductivity measurement. The conductivity was measured at $32.4^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. The results are represented graphically in the case of sol H. The cell constant of the cell employed was 1.743 Cm^{-1} .

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FIG. 1

DISCUSSION

Effect on Ageing: Ageing results in increasing the conductivity of the sol. This is the usual effect of ageing which gradually renders the sol unstable. The increase in conductivity is more evident in diluted sols. Ageing results in aggregation of particles which will result in slight decrease of conductivity. On the other hand, part of the electrolyte adsorbed in the micelles comes out resulting in increase in conductivity⁴.

Effect on Dilution: Dilution with sucrose solution results in decrease in equivalent conductivity or increase in R_0 on dilution. Further dilution results in decrease of R_0 or increase of equivalent conductivity. Hence the system behaves as a colloidal electrolyte like the soap solution⁶ and other colloidal systems⁷. On the other hand when the sol is diluted with water, equivalent conductivity continuously increases and the sol is gradually rendered unstable. It is obvious that presence of sucrose is essential for the stability of the sol. Hence the micelles contain hydroxyl as a stabilizing ion partly derived from ammonia and partly derived from sucrose solution. In absence of either of these substances, the micelles will immediately break down. There is considerable adsorption of chloride in the micelles. However, it appears to be physically held and may not play any fundamental role in micelle formation. The role of sucrose may be compared to the role of organic substances in floatation processes.

Effect of purity on Conductivity: The specific conductivity of the sols E and F were determined graphically (Data not reported). Specific conductivity decreases on purity as has been observed by other workers also.^{8,9}

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